

HISTORY

TOLERANCE AND MULTICULTURALISM TRADITIONS IN AZERBAIJAN: FROM THE PAST TO THE PRESENT

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Abstract

The article covers the work done in Azerbaijan to preserve the traditions of tolerance and multiculturalism. It is noted that since ancient times Azerbaijan has been being inhabited by different peoples and religions, maintaining friendly relations and inter-ethnic cooperation, which is one of the features of ethno-confessional situation when no one is subjected to intolerance and discrimination. The article describes the measures taken by the Republic of Azerbaijan to preserve this tradition, promote it and bring it to the future generations. It is mentioned that Azerbaijan is a unique example and has wide experience in this field; it has close ties with the religious centers, existing in the world, carries out repair and restoration works in religious monuments belonging to different religions. It is noted that the main purpose of the heavenly religions is to call people to purity, to promote the sacred values, to ensure peace and tranquility. The article also points out the realities of history, namely the fact that religious intolerance and discrimination take society and peoples to the abyss, and the state to the destruction. It is mentioned that in case of this fact being ignored people face serious tortures.

Keywords: state, religion, confession, cooperation, tolerance, propaganda, confrontation.

Recent negative events in the world prove that the foundation of stability is built upon the establishment of peace and mutual understanding among people. Stability and progress cannot exist in a society that fails to recognize cultural diversity and lacks respect for the traditions, lifestyles, and beliefs of individuals from other religions.

In today's world, the religious factor contributes significantly to destabilization, especially in Muslim countries, and external forces often manipulate this situation. The process is clearly visible in the work of numerous ideological movements established by specific people and institutions.

Considering this reality, many countries across the globe prioritize the development of tolerance in inter-faith relationships and the creation of conditions for the peaceful coexistence of representatives of various religions and cultures. The growth of intolerance in society results in the escalation of human relationships and the creation of new conflict areas globally. To prevent confrontations, it is vital to promote the principles of tolerance and respect towards representatives of other religions and cultures.

History proves that religious disagreements between people of different religions and denominations have caused wars, taking the lives of innocent people. These tensions arose from the spread of religious intolerance and fanaticism in society, causing irreversible consequences. Even today, this threat remains a critical issue in many countries across the globe.

Recent events on both global and regional levels show that religions, which seek to spread high moral and ethical values, reinforce unity and equality among people, and maintain peace and stability, can at times be turned into instruments for pursuing political interests, executing sinister plots, and provoking conflicts among people.

Those who reject all religions except their own and believe their faith to be the only right one often take a hardline position against other faiths, resulting in mass tragedies — from the killing of innocent people to the destruction of religious shrines and the total destruction of countries. All divine religions teach their followers to exhibit tolerance and justice toward people of other faiths, regarding any attempts to divide or create differences based on religious or sectarian identities as a sin (1, p. 85).

Azerbaijan, known as the cradle of Zoroastrianism, was home to a Christian state in the first millennium, and today Muslims, Christians, and Jews live together here in harmony and tolerance (2, p. 267).

Azerbaijan today stands as a unique model of peaceful coexistence between various nationalities and faiths. Our country has created the conditions for representatives of all religions to practice their faith freely and carry out religious ceremonies and rituals.

For centuries, Azerbaijan has been a land of religious coexistence, where people of different faiths have lived in peace and harmony, actively contributing to the socio-political life of the country while safeguarding their religious beliefs, traditions, and ethnic heritage. Our state's history has never witnessed cases of national, racial, or religious discrimination, hostility, or conflicts (3, p. 35).

Azerbaijan has historically been a sanctuary for those who encountered religious intolerance, including followers of different religions and denominations subjected to persecution for various reasons. Here, they never felt like outsiders, smoothly blending into the local society, establishing family ties, and fostering unity with the native inhabitants.

The people of Azerbaijan have always endeavored to promote friendship and brotherhood among various

ethnic and religious communities in the country, creating an environment of peace and mutual understanding. This legacy of humanism is still preserved today.

The Azerbaijani people's intrinsic tolerance for other religions and cultures, along with their aspiration for mutual understanding, is founded on their nature, humanity, and kindness. In today's world, religious affiliation affects the geographic distribution of people in some countries. Jews, Christians, Muslims, and followers of other religions live in separate neighborhoods. In Azerbaijan, at the intersection of civilizations, people of different religions coexist on the same street, in the same courtyard, or even in the same house, sharing their holidays and religious ceremonies.

The Constitution of Azerbaijan guarantees equal treatment of all religious beliefs under the law. This principle is secured not just by law, but also in the reality of daily life. In Azerbaijan, the law prohibits the propaganda of one religion's superiority over others

Azerbaijan hosts active religious communities of various Christian denominations — Orthodoxy, Catholicism, and Protestantism. Most Christians in our country follow the Orthodox faith. Following the decision of the Azerbaijani government, the building of the Holy Myrrhbearers Cathedral, which was constructed in 1907 by the well-known Azerbaijani benefactor Haji Zeynalabdin Taghiyev and closed in 1920, was handed over to the Russian Orthodox Church in 1991. In May 2001, while on a visit to Azerbaijan, Patriarch Alexy II visited the church and assigned it the status of the main cathedral. In the Soviet era, the church was repurposed as a warehouse, leading to considerable destruction. An Azerbaijani businessman living in Moscow, Aydin Kurbanov, took it upon himself to restore the church. Before long, the church was fully restored and welcomed worshippers once more. The event was attended by Heydar Aliyev, members of the government, and embassy representatives (4, p. 72).

In the years 1999-2001, Baku saw the revival of yet another Orthodox sanctuary — the Cathedral of the Nativity of the Blessed Virgin Mary. In 1998, the Baku and Caspian Diocese was established in Azerbaijan, incorporating Orthodox churches from Azerbaijan and the republics of Dagestan and Chechnya. In the future, this structure became known as the Baku and Azerbaijan Diocese of the Russian Orthodox Church. At present, Baku has three Russian Orthodox churches, while Ganja, Khachmaz, and Sumgayit each have one.

Patriarch Bartholomew II of Constantinople visited Azerbaijan in April 2003 to examine the religious situation and support the development of interfaith dialogue. He had meetings with state officials, the clergy, and the leaders of Muslim, Christian, and Jewish communities, expressing his appreciation for the harmonious relations between the religious groups in the country. Our National Leader, Heydar Aliyev, also met with the guest and held an extensive conversation with him.

In May 1992, the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Vatican, the center of global Catholic Christianity, established diplomatic ties. The official visit of National Leader Heydar Aliyev to the Vatican on September 26, 1997, played a crucial role in enhancing the relations between the two countries. He held a meeting with

Pope John Paul II, and they discussed the activities of the Catholic Church in Azerbaijan.

In 1999, the Catholic religious community was officially registered, and on May 22, 2002, Pope John Paul II visited Azerbaijan for the first time, meeting with government officials and public figures. He highlighted the high level of religious tolerance in our country and emphasized that the Azerbaijani model of interfaith agreement and tolerance could be an exemplary model for many countries worldwide.

In the subsequent years, relations with the Vatican became even more solid. During his official visit to Italy in February 2005, President Ilham Aliyev visited the Vatican, where he met with Secretary of State Cardinal Angelo Sodano to discuss bilateral relations.

On March 6, 2008, Cardinal Tarcisio Bertone, Secretary of State of the Holy See, visited Azerbaijan. On March 7, he met with President Ilham Aliyev, where it was noted that the country has a high level of interfaith tolerance. On that day, the Catholic Church of St. Mary was opened in Baku, with the solemn ceremony attended by President Ilham Aliyev and Cardinal Bertone. President Ilham Aliyev stated in his speech that the opening of the Catholic Church in Baku would serve as an important step for Azerbaijan's progress, its integration into the global community, and the strengthening of relations with Europe.

On October 2, 2016, Pope Francis visited Azerbaijan, meeting with President Ilham Aliyev, public figures, and religious representatives, and also attended a religious ceremony at the Catholic Church in Baku. The visit of Pope Francis to Azerbaijan opened a new chapter in the bilateral ties between the two countries.

The Udis, a small ethnic group predominantly living in the village of Nij, Gabala region, are one of the ethnic groups under state protection in Azerbaijan. The Udi population worldwide is about 10,000, and approximately 4,000 of them live in Nij village of the Gabala region. For centuries, Azerbaijanis and Udis have coexisted peacefully, with strong bonds of friendship and mutual understanding.

Due to the attention and care of the Azerbaijani government, the Albanian-Udi religious community was officially registered in 2003. In 1836, by a decree of the Russian emperor, the Albanian Apostolic Church was placed under the jurisdiction of the Armenian Apostolic Church. Due to the successful religious policy of the Azerbaijani government, the Udi community were able to restore their lost rights. One of these monuments is the Albanian Church-Museum in the village of Kish, Sheki region, which is considered one of the oldest Christian temples both in the Caucasus and globally. The church, dating back to the 4th-5th centuries, was fully restored and reopened in 2003. Along with foreign experts, Azerbaijani scientists played a key role in the restoration of the church.

In May 2006, the opening ceremony of the Albanian-Udi Chotari Church was held in Nij village, Gabala region, with the participation of government officials, religious community leaders, and international guests (5, p. 152).

The Jews are one of the ancient peoples living in Azerbaijan. Throughout the centuries, Jews escaping

persecution in their countries of residence have found sanctuary in Azerbaijan, where they live in an environment of peace and mutual understanding. They have never faced religious intolerance or discrimination in our country; on the contrary, they have always been treated with attention and care by the local residents (6, p. 35). In the post-Soviet space, Red Sloboda in the Guba region is the only area where Jews live in a compact community. Azerbaijan is, to this day, one of the few countries where Jews are greeted with warmth and kindness.

The Jewish population in Azerbaijan consists of three communities: Mountain Jews, Ashkenazi Jews (European Jews), and Georgian Jews. There are about 16,000 Jews residing in our country. The Mountain Jews make up 11,000 of this total, with around 6,000 living in Baku, 4,000 in Guba, and 1,000 spread across other cities. The number of Ashkenazi Jews is roughly 4,000, whereas the Georgian Jewish population stands at about 700. As of now, seven Jewish religious communities are officially registered in Azerbaijan, while Baku, Oghuz, and Guba each have two functioning synagogues.

Due to the Azerbaijani government's support, a new Jewish synagogue was opened in Baku in March 2003, and the first Jewish secondary school was established in September of that year. The opening ceremonies were attended by the government officials, representatives of religious communities in Azerbaijan, and international guests. Apart from Jewish organizations, the Caucasus Muslims Board and the Baku and Azerbaijan Diocese of the Russian Orthodox Church were actively involved in the synagogue's construction. Muslims and Christians taking part in the construction of a Jewish synagogue and providing their support is an unprecedented event on a global scale.

It is important to highlight that, on a range of major issues, Jews have backed Azerbaijanis, and both peoples have always stood united in their fight against a common enemy (7, p. 127).

The significant rise in the number of religious sites, including mosques, churches, and synagogues, during Azerbaijan's independence period serves as a key indicator that strengthening tolerance has become a vital part of state policy. By the time Azerbaijan restored its independence, the country had only 18 mosques (8, p. 136).

Currently, the country has 2,258 functioning mosques, 748 pilgrimage sites, 16 churches, and 7 synagogues. As of today, 995 religious communities are officially registered in the country, including 957 Islamic and 38 non-Islamic ones — 27 Christian, 8 Jewish, 2 Bahá'í, and 1 associated with the Krishna Consciousness Society (9, p. 171).

The national leader of Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, played a crucial role in the protection and strengthening of religious tolerance traditions in Azerbaijan. Following his return to power, significant progress was made in the state-religion relationship, with a focus on advancing national and spiritual values, as well as taking crucial steps to resolve issues in the religious sector.

Thanks to the support of the national leader Heydar Aliyev, old mosques were renovated, new ones

were constructed, the Bibi-Heybat mosque, demolished in 1936, was rebuilt, and new religious schools were opened across the country (10, p. 222).

Under Heydar Aliyev, Azerbaijan paid special attention to maintaining its long-standing traditions of tolerance and multiculturalism, making the strengthening of religious tolerance a fundamental priority in state religious policy. Heydar Aliyev frequently engaged with religious leaders of different faiths, visited places of worship, delivered speeches to the faithful, and extended his congratulations on religious celebrations and ceremonies (11, p. 131).

President Ilham Aliyev is currently implementing this policy with notable success and long-term vision. Today, the protection and support of followers of various religions in the country remain a fundamental aspect of Azerbaijan's state religious policy.

President Ilham Aliyev prioritizes the effective regulation of state-religion relations in our country, the preservation of traditions of tolerance, and the renovation and restoration of religious heritage sites. He regularly engages with religious community leaders, addressing their concerns and needs.

Due to the dedication and support of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, several mosques and historical cultural landmarks have been extensively renovated and restored in recent years, including the Tazapir, Ajdarbay, and Shamakhi mosques, as well as the Bibi-Heybat sacred site and the Imamzade mausoleums in Ganja and Barda. Furthermore, the Heydar Mosque was built in Baku, renowned for its breathtaking architecture and unique style.

The state also extends special attention to religious communities, allocating financial aid from the state budget, and ensuring that religious holidays and celebrations are conducted at the state level. This reflects the significant attention the Azerbaijani government gives to religious communities (12, p. 384).

Under the direct guidance of President Ilham Aliyev, the Service of the State Advisor on Multinational, Multicultural and Religious Affairs was established in February 2014 to ensure a more effective regulation of state religious policy, bolster the traditions of religious tolerance, and enhance state support for ethnic and religious communities in Azerbaijan, and the Baku International Multiculturalism Center was launched in May. The Service of the State Advisor is now pursuing coordinated and purposeful actions to manage state religious policy, protect the rights of all ethnic and religious communities residing in Azerbaijan, and bolster the country's deep-rooted traditions of tolerance.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation is also actively involved in promoting and strengthening the traditions of religious tolerance in Azerbaijan. Through its initiatives, the foundation has successfully restored numerous religious monuments, representing both Christianity and Islam. The foundation is currently working closely with the Apostolic Prefecture of the Catholic Church in Azerbaijan. In 2008, the foundation and the mentioned organization signed a memorandum of cooperation, and in 2009, with the foundation's support, restoration work was undertaken at the Catholic Church of the Virgin Mary's Immaculate Conception in Baku.

On February 23, 2016, the Vatican hosted the opening ceremony of the restored Catacombs of Marcellinus and Peter, attended by Azerbaijan's First Lady Mehriban Aliyeva. The restoration efforts were supported by the Heydar Aliyev Foundation. This reflects Azerbaijan's commitment to preserving cultural and religious monuments, both within its borders and in different parts of the world.

These facts serve as evidence of Azerbaijan's commitment to providing equal legal conditions for all religions, fostering a culture of tolerance, and ensuring that the government respects the rights of all peoples and ethnic groups, with a particular focus on preserving and studying their historical and cultural heritage.

It is safe to say that in Azerbaijan today, all initiatives aimed at reinforcing the traditions of tolerance are implemented systematically and with clear intent, fostering an environment where people of different faiths can live and work as equals.

In today's world, the greatest responsibility is to study this rich heritage more profoundly, preserve it, and pass it on to future generations. It is a solemn historical duty borne by every Azerbaijani citizen.

Tolerance stands as a unique national and cultural asset of Azerbaijan, setting an example for nations worldwide. The people of Azerbaijan will preserve their time-honored traditions of tolerance, ensuring they endure for future generations, and will decisively resist any efforts to undermine them.

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